

HETEROSIS STUDIES IN FOR SEED COTTON YIELD AND ITS COMPONENTS IN DESI COTTON (*Gossypium arboreum* L.)S. B. Borgaonkar¹, Sayli Gaikwad², A. B. Jadhav³ and G. S. Pawar⁴

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MS Received: 04.08.2024; MS Revised:29.04.2024; MS Accepted:30.08.2024)

MS 3237 (RESEARCH PAPER IN AGRICULTURAL BOTANY,)

Abstract

Thirty crosses were evaluated for average heterosis, heterobeltiosis and standard heterosis. The magnitude of heterosis, heterobeltiosis and standard heterosis were found significant for all the characters studied. The magnitude of heterosis, heterobeltiosis and standard heterosis for all the characters in the present study was highly appreciable. Out of thirty crosses, seventeen crosses showed highly positive and significant standard heterosis for seed cotton yield per plant. Out of thirty crosses, the crosses showed highly significant and desirable standard heterosis for various traits viz., cross PA 785 x PA 810 for number of bolls per plant, for upper half mean length; cross PA 904 x PA 402 for uniformity ratio; PA 904 x PA 402 for number of sympodia / plant; PA 785 x PA 810 for days to 50 per cent flowering; PA 904 x PA 402 for boll weight; PA 873 x JLA 505 for plant height; PA 785 x PA 810 for days to maturity; PA 785 x PA 08 for fibre fineness (micronaire); PA 785 x JLA 505 for fibre strength; and PA 809 x AKA 8 for ginning outturn were found most superior cross combinations for respective characters. The cross-combination PA 904 x PA 402 (61.60 %) displayed significantly positive average heterosis for seed cotton yield per plant followed by PA 785 x PA 810 (44.91 %) and CNA 1032 x PA 402 (40.20 %). In case of better parent heterosis, the cross PA 904 x PA 402 (58.14 %) recorded highly significant positive heterosis followed by the crosses PA 785 x PA 810 (41.82 %) and CNA 1032 x PA 402 (35.73 %).

Key Words - Heterosis, Standard heterosis, Micronaire, Staple length

Introduction

Cotton (*Gossypium spp.*) is a crop of prosperity having influence on man and matter and called as 'King of fibre'. It is also rightly called as 'White Gold'. Cotton is one of the most important commercial crops and forms the back bone of Indian textile industry. Global cotton production faces many challenges in the 21st century. Between the rapid increase in human population and the loss of arable land due to soil erosion, soil salinization, harsher climate conditions and urbanization, the demand for promoting cotton yield is increasing dramatically. Establishing research initiatives to tackle these challenges depends on identifying the major factors that limit increases in yield. It is grown commercially in the temperate and tropical regions of more than 70 countries. India is perhaps the first country to make use of cotton. Cotton, the 'white gold' enjoys a pre-eminent status among all cash crops in the country. It is grown commercially in the temperate and tropical regions of more than 70 countries. Specific areas of production include countries such as China, USA, India, Pakistan, Uzbekistan, Turkey, Australia, Greece, Brazil, Egypt etc. where climatic conditions suit the natural growth requirements of cotton, which includes periods of hot and dry weather and adequate moisture obtained through irrigation. Genetic improvement in *desi* cotton could be gained either through selection or exploitation of hybrid vigour. Therefore, more emphasis should be given to increase the seed cotton yield per unit area by developing hybrids with short stature, big boll size and longer staple length with sustained yield in multiple environments. To achieve such desirable characteristics in a new cultivar, proper breeding strategies should be followed. There is an urgent need to promote those cottons that could come closer in quality to the most sought by modern textile mills. For development of superior and heterotic hybrids in cotton, it is essential to utilize large number of available germplasm. In the context of quality assessment, high volume instrument testing is universally accepted by the industry and is becoming a requirement, enabling cotton to be marketed more directly on textile mill needs rather than the traditional grade, staple and micronaire. This has contributed to the development and acceptance of high quality hybrids and varieties. In heterosis breeding programme, the selection of crosses on basis of heterosis is very important in producing superior hybrids.

Material and Methods

The present investigation was undertaken to Study of heterosis for seed cotton yield, yield contributing and fibre quality traits in *desi* Cotton (*Gossypium arboreum* L.). Twenty four cross combinations derived by

crossing six lines with four testers in line x tester mating design. The experiment material consisted of 30 crosses eleven parents along with two standard checks (PA 740 and PA 812). The experiment was conducted at Cotton Research Station, Mahboob Baugh farm, Vasantrao Naik Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeeth, Parbhani during *kharif* season of 2023-24. The mean values of all the treatments for the characters under study were worked out. Standard error and critical difference at 1 and 5 per cent level of significance were calculated by using the formula (Panse and Sukhatme, 1989). The magnitude of heterosis was estimated for all the characters under study over mid parent, better parent and standard check.

Results and Discussion

The analysis of variance showed significant differences for all the characters studied. The mean sum of squares for the treatments were highly significant for various characters studied. The analysis of variance for all the characters is presented in Table No. 1. The heterosis over mid parent, better parent and standard checks were presented in Table No. 2. Top five hybrids with fibre quality characters are presented in Table No. 3.

Earliness in flowering is desirable and hence the cross combinations having negative heterosis for days to 50 per cent flowering are desirable. The crosses PA 833 x PA 402 (-11.52 %) and PA 809 x JLA 505 (-9.38 %) recorded significantly negative heterosis over mid parent. The cross PA 823 x PA 402 (-12.57 %) exhibited highly significant and negative heterosis followed by cross combination PA 785 x PA 810 (-12.12 %) and PA 809 x JLA 505 (-9.94 %). The cross combination PA 833 x PA 402 (-10.98 % over standard check PA 740), (-11.52 % over standard check PA 812) and PA 785 x AKA 8 (-9.15 % over standard check PA 740), (-9.70 % over standard check PA 812) displayed significant negative standard heterosis, respectively. Fourteen cross combinations each exhibited highly significant and negative heterosis over standard check PA 740 and PA 812, respectively. Similar kind of heterosis for earliness was reported by Giri *et al.* (2006) and Preetha and Ravindran *et al.* (2008). The cross combinations PA 785 x PA 810 (-8.61 %), PA 785 x JLA 505 (-6.03 %) and PA 833 x JLA 505 (-5.57 %), had recorded desirable heterosis for days to maturity. Heterosis over better parent was ranged from -9.72 per cent (PA 785 x PA 810) to 8.15 per cent (PA 904 x AKA 8). The cross PA 785 x PA 810 (-9.72 %) exhibited highest significant negative heterosis followed by PA 833 x PA 402 (-8.16 %), PA 809 x PA 08 (-8.03 %), PA 809 x PA 810 (-7.29) and PA 809 x JLA 505 (-7.08 %). The crosses PA 785 x PA 810, PA 809 x JLA 505 and

CNA 1032 x AKA 8 (-10.44 %) exhibited highest significant negative heterosis for days to maturity over check PA 812 followed by the crosses PA 833 x PA 402 and PA 809 x AKA 8 (-9.64). Similar results for days to maturity was reported by Choudhary *et al.* (2014), Solanki *et al.* (2014), Sharma *et al.* (2016) and Khuwaja *et al.* (2022)

Amongst 30 crosses, seventeen crosses exhibited significant positive heterosis over mid parent for plant height. The cross combination CNA 1032 x PA 402 (25.34 %) recorded significantly positive heterosis over mid parent followed by PA 785 x PA 402 (19.64 %) and PA 785 x JLA 505 (16.25 %). The crosses CNA 1032 x PA 402 (25.34 %) and PA 785 x PA 402 (19.37%) recorded highly significant and positive heterosis over better parent. Two cross combinations PA 785 x JLA 505 (6.90 over standard check PA 740 and 10.71 % over standard check PA 812), and PA 873 x JLA 505 (7.28 over standard check PA 740 and 11.11 % over standard check PA 812) exhibited significantly positive standard heterosis. These findings are in accordance with the results reported by Dawod *et al.* (2010), Tigga *et al.* (2017) and Vavdiya *et al.* (2019).

Highly significant and positive heterosis over mid parent for number of sympodia per plant was exhibited by PA 809 x AKA 8 (52.54 %) followed by PA 904 x PA 402 (46.88 %) and PA 809 x PA 08 (43.86 %). However significant positive heterosis over mid parent was exhibited by seven hybrids. The cross PA 809 x AKA 8 (40.63%) exhibited highly positive and significant heterosis over better parent. The crosses having positive significant standard heterosis over standard check were PA 873 x JLA 505 (30.56% over standard check PA 740 and PA 812) and PA 785 x PA 810 (25.00 % over standard check PA 740), PA 833 x PA 810 (30.56 % over standard check PA 740), PA 809 x AKA 8 (25.00% over standard check PA 740). Six crosses reported positive significant standard heterosis over PA 740. The results are in accordance with the reports of Tigga *et al.* (2017), Bhandavi *et al.* (2018), Vavdiya *et al.* (2019) and Keerthivarman *et al.* (2022).

The cross PA 904 x PA 402 (43.33%) displayed highest significant positive mid-parent heterosis for number of bolls per plant followed by PA 809 x JLA 505 (38.98 %) and PA 785 x PA 402 (33.33 %), whereas, the cross combination CNA 1032 x AKA 8 (-33.33 %) exhibited significant negative heterosis over mid-parent. In case of heterobeltiosis the cross combination PA 904 x PA 402 (38.71 %) displayed highest significant positive heterosis followed by the crosses PA 809 x JLA 505 (28.13 %) and PA 785 x PA 402 (25.71%), while significantly negative heterobeltiosis was reported by the cross combination PA 833 x PA 402. The cross combination PA 785 x PA 810 displayed highest significant standard heterosis over standard checks PA 740 (32.35 %) and PA 812 (25.00 %) followed by PA 785 x PA 505 over check PA 740 (29.41%) and PA 812 (22.22 %) and PA 904 x PA 402 over check PA 740 (26.47 %) and PA 812 (19.44%). Eleven and six crosses each recorded positive and significant standard heterosis over checks PA 740 and PA 812 respectively. Heterosis for this trait was also reported by the earlier workers viz; Chakholoma *et al.* (2021) and Keerthivarman *et al.* (2022). The range of mid-parent heterosis was from -13.49 per cent (PA 785 x AKA 8) to 10.81 per cent (CNA 1032 x PA 402) for ginning outturn. The crosses PA 809 x AKA 8 (9.27 %) and CNA 1032 x PA 402 (10.81%) recorded highly significant and positive heterosis over mid-parent. The range of better parent heterosis was from -16.17 per cent (PA 873 X PA 402) to 6.55 per cent (PA 809 x AKA 8) for ginning outturn. Only three cross combinations exhibited significant positive standard heterosis over the check PA 812. The most significant positive heterotic crosses were PA 904 x PA 402 (14.10), CNA 1032 x PA 402 (13.40) and PA 809 x AKA 8 (12.53). Similar results were reported by Vavdiya *et al.* (2019), Chinchane *et al.* (2020), Chakholoma *et al.* (2021) and Keerthivarman *et al.* (2022).

The average heterosis for upper half mean length ranged from - 14.95 per cent (PA 904 x AKA 8) to 9.47 per cent (PA 904 x PA 402). The crosses viz., PA 904 x PA 402 (9.47 %), PA 809 X PA 402 (8.43 %) and

PA 833 x PA 08 (7.52 %) recorded significantly positive heterosis over mid parent. Fifteen hybrids displayed significant positive heterosis over mid- parent for upper half mean length. In case of heterobeltiosis only two hybrids i.e. PA 809 x PA 08 (6.51 %) and PA 904 x PA 402 (5.75 %) recorded highest significant positive heterobeltiosis for span length. The heterobeltiosis ranged from -16.72 per cent (PA 904 x AKA 8) to 6.51 per cent (PA 809 x PA 08). Fourteen hybrids recorded significant positive standard heterosis over check PA 740. The crosses PA 785 x PA 810 (7.62 %) and PA 904 x PA 402 (7.62 %) recorded highly significant and positive heterosis over standard check PA 740 followed by PA 809 x PA 08 (7.27%). Similar results were obtained by Geddani *et al.* (2011), Babu *et al.* (2018), Chakholoma *et al.* (2021) and Hottigodar *et al.* (2023).

For fibre fineness, twenty two crosses recorded significant negative heterosis over mid-parent. The cross combination PA 904 x AKA 8 (-3.96 %) displayed the highest significant negative heterosis over mid-parent followed by CNA 1032 x AKA 8 (-3.36 %). Twenty four crosses showed significant negative heterosis over better parent. The cross PA 785 x AKA 8 (-33.06 %) exhibited highest significant negative heterosis over better parent followed by PA 809 x AKA 8 (-29.03 %) and PA 785 x PA 08 (-26.55 %). Nine and eight crosses each recorded significant negative heterosis over check PA 740 and PA 812 respectively. The cross combination PA 785 x PA 08 displayed significantly negative economic heterosis over standard check PA 740 (-13.54) and PA 812 (-11.70), respectively. Similar results were reported by Babu *et al.* (2018), Chakholoma *et al.* (2021), Heba *et al.* (2021) and Hottigodar *et al.* (2023).

The mid-parent heterosis for fibre strength ranged from -21.45 per cent (PA 809 x PA 810 to 14.31 per cent (PA 785 x PA 402). Fifteen crosses recorded significant positive heterosis over mid-parent for fibre strength. The cross PA 785 x PA 402 (14.31 %) recorded highest significant positive average heterosis followed by PA 809 x AKA 8 (13.98 %) and PA 809 x PA 08 (12.83 %). Thirteen crosses recorded significantly positive heterosis over better parent for fibre strength. The cross combination PA 809 x AKA 8 (12.79 %) recorded highly significant and positive heterosis followed by PA 785 x PA 402 (12.59 %) over better parent. Sixteen crosses each exhibited significant positive standard heterosis over check PA 812. The cross combination PA 785 x JLA 505 showed highest significant positive heterosis over standard check PA 812 (10.85 %) and PA 740 (10.24 %) followed by PA 809 x PA 08 over standard check PA 812 (9.93 %) and PA 740 (9.32 %). Similar results were reported by Heba *et al.* (2021), Shinde *et al.* (2021) and Hottigodar *et al.* (2023).

Out of thirty crosses, nineteen crosses recorded significant positive heterosis for uniformity ratio over mid-parent. The cross combination PA 904 x PA 402 (8.97 %) recorded highest significant positive heterosis followed by PA 809 x JLA 505 (8.74 %) and PA 904 x JLA 505 (8.50 %). The range of mid parent heterosis was from -10.56 per cent (PA 785 x AKA 8) to 8.97 per cent (PA 904 x PA 402). Seventeen cross combination recorded significant positive heterosis over better parent. Fifteen crosses exhibited significant positive standard heterosis over check PA 812, whereas seventeen crosses each exhibited significant positive standard heterosis over check PA 740. The cross combination PA 904 x PA 402 (5.59 %) showed highest significant positive standard heterosis over standard check PA 812 (5.59 %) and PA 740 (6.92 %). Heterosis for uniformity ratio was reported by the earlier workers viz; Chakholoma *et al.* (2021), Heba *et al.* (2021), Shinde *et al.* (2021) and Hottigodar *et al.* (2023).

The cross combination PA 904 x PA 402 (61.60 %) displayed significantly positive average heterosis for seed cotton yield per plant followed by PA 785 x PA 810 (44.91 %) and CNA 1032 x PA 402 (40.20 %). Twenty two cross combinations recorded significant positive heterosis over mid-parent for this trait. The range of average heterosis observed was from -29.73 per cent (CNA 1032 x AKA 8) to 61.60 (PA

904 x PA 402). In case of better parent heterosis, the cross PA 904 x PA 402 (58.14 %) recorded highly significant positive heterosis followed by the crosses PA 785 x PA 810 (41.82 %) and CNA 1032 x PA 402 (35.73 %). Among thirty crosses, twenty one crosses exhibited significantly positive heterosis over better parent. The cross combination PA 904 x PA 402 displayed the highly significant positive standard heterosis over the standard check PA 740 (52.28 %) and PA 812 (42.15 %) followed by PA 785 x PA 810 over check PA 740 (42.02 %) and PA 812 (32.58 %) and CNA 1032 x PA 402 over check PA 740 (39.60 %) and PA 812 (30.32 %). The range of standard heterosis was -31.58 to 52.58 per cent over check PA 740 and -31.91 to 52.28 per cent over check PA 812. Twenty one and seventeen crosses each recorded significant positive standard heterosis over standard checks PA 740 and PA 812 respectively. Heterosis for this trait was also reported by Chinchane *et al.* (2020), Gopal *et al.* (2020), Chakholoma *et al.* (2021), Keerthivarman *et al.* (2022), Vaid *et al.* (2022) and Hottigodar *et al.* (2023).

Conclusion :

The hybrids PA 904 x PA 402, PA 785 x PA 810 and CNA 1032 x PA 402 were found to be highly heterotic for seed cotton yield and fibre quality traits. Hence these hybrids could be exploited for standard heterosis after testing at multilocations and seasons before release for commercial cultivation.

Acknowledgement:

We are highly thankful to Head, Department of Agricultural Botany, College of Agriculture, Parbhani and Cotton Breeder for providing all facilities to conduct the experiment.

Declaration of Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no potential conflict of interest.

References:

- Babu, B. J., Satish, Y., Ahamed, M. L. and Rao, V. S. (2018). Studies on heterosis in cotton (*Gossypium hirsutum* L.) for yield and fibre quality traits. *International Journal of Chemical Studies*, 6(4): 1013-1018.
- Bhandavi, R. D., Kalpande, H. V., Chinchane, V. N. and Anil, K. (2018). Heterosis studies for seed cotton yield and yield contributing traits in *desi* cotton (*Gossypium arboreum* L.). *Journal of Cotton Research and Development*, 32(2): 207-212.
- Chakholoma, M., Nimbale, S., Sangwan, O., Mor, V. and Jain, A. (2021). Studies on economic heterosis for yield and fibre quality traits in American cotton (*Gossypium hirsutum* L.). *J. Cotton Res. Dev.*, 35(2), 185-192.
- Chhavikant, K. S., Kumar, A. and Pundir, S. R. (2017). Heterosis studies for seed cotton yield and other traits in upland cotton (*Gossypium hirsutum* L.). *J. Pharma. and Phyto.*, 6(6), 583-586.
- Chinchane, V. N., Deosarkar, D. B., Baig, K. S. and Kalpande, H. V. (2020). Combining ability analysis for fibre quality traits in *desi* cotton (*Gossypium arboreum* L.) across the environments. *Int. J. Curr. Microbiol. App. Sci.*, 9 (1): 1885-1896.
- Choudhary, R. Solanki, B. G., Choudhary, R., Singh, A. K. and Khandelwal, V. (2014). Heterosis in single cross inter and intraspecific hybrids of *desi* cotton in relation to seed cotton yield and its contributing characters. *Biosci*, 9: 839-43.
- Dawod, K. M. and Al-Guboory, K. K. (2010). Heterosis and combining ability in diallel crossing among cultivars of upland cotton. *Bulletin of Faculty of Agriculture, Cairo University.*, 61 (1): 1-7.
- Geddani, S. B., B. M. Khadi, Suma Mogali, R. S. Patil, I. S. Katageri, H. L. Nadaf and Patil B.C. (2011). Study of heterosis in genetic male sterility based diploid cotton hybrids for yield, yield component and fibre quality characters. *Karnataka J. Agric. Sci.*, 24 (2):118- 124.
- Giri, R. K., Nirannia, K. S., Dutt, Y. and Sangwan, R. S. (2006). Combining ability studies for yield and quality traits in upland cotton (*Gossypium hirsutum* L.). *J. Cotton Res.Dev.*, 20 (2): 178-180.
- Gopal, G. R., Deosarkar, D. B. and Chinchane, V. N. (2020). Heterosis studies in CMS based and conventional hybrids for yield and yield contributing traits in cotton (*Gossypium hirsutum* L.) over the environments. *Int. J. Curr. Microbiol. App. Sci.*, 9 (3): 1212-1227.
- Heba H.E., Hamed and S.R.N. Said, (2021). Estimation of heterosis and combining ability for yield and fibre quality traits by using Line x Tester analysis in cotton (*Gossypium barbadense* L.). *Menoufia J. Plant Prod.*, 6: 35-51.
- Hottigodar, H.V. Kalpande and V.N. Chinchane, (2023). Heterosis study on yield contributing and fibre quality traits in *desi* cotton (*Gossypium arboreum* L.). *The Pharma Inno. J.*, 2023; 12(2): 491-495.
- Keerthivarman, K., Mahalingam, L., Premalatha, N., Boopathi, N. M., Senguttuvan, K. and Manivannan, A. (2022). Combining ability and heterosis studies in cotton (*Gossypium hirsutum* L.) for yield and fibre quality traits. *Ele. J. of Pl. Breed.*, 13(2): 697-704.
- Khuwaja, S., Bux, H., Abro, S., Rizwan, M. and Kaleri, G. M. (2022). Estimate of heterosis and heterobeltiosis for the improvement of yield in upland cotton (*Gossypium hirsutum* L.). *Pak. J. of Agri., Agricultural Engg. and Vet. Sci.*, 38(1): 1-6.
- Panse, V. G. and Sukhatme, P. V. (Revised by Sukhatme, P. V. and Amble, V. N.) (1989). Statistical methods for agricultural workers. ICAR publication, New Delhi.
- Preetha, S. and Raveendran, T. S. (2008). Combining ability and heterosis for yield and quality traits in line x tester crosses of upland cotton (*Gossypium hirsutum* L.). *Int. J. of Pl. Breed. and Genet.*, 2(2): 64-74.
- Sharma, R., Gill, B. S. and Pathak, D. (2016). Heterobeltiosis for yield, its component traits and fibre properties in upland cotton (*Gossypium hirsutum* L.). *J. Cotton Res. Dev.*, 30 (1): 11-15.
- Shinde, A. V., Deosarkar, D. B., Chinchane, V. N., Deshmukh, A. S. and Thakur, N. R. (2021). Study on heterosis for fibre quality traits in intra (*G. arboreum* x *G. arboreum*) and interspecific (*G. herbaceum* x *G. arboreum*) crosses of *desi* cotton. *The Pharma Inno. J.*, 2021; 10(12): 1100-1104.
- Solanki, H. V., Mehta, D. R. and Valu, V. R. M. (2014). Heterosis for seed cotton yield and its contributing characters in cotton (*Gossypium hirsutum* L.). *Ele. J. of Pl. Breed.*, 5(1): 124-130.
- S. B. Thawari, V. V. Kalpande, R. B. Ghorade, 2022, "Heterosis Studies For Grain Mold Resistance And Its Associated Parameters In Kharif Sorghum" VOL. XII, ISSUE XXXIV, Oct 2022 Multilogic In Science ISSN 2277-7601, Page 319-321.
- Tigga, A., Patil, S. S., Edke, V., Roy, U. and Kumar, A. (2017). Heterosis and inbreeding depression for seed cotton yield and yield attributing traits in intra-hirsutum (*G. hirsutum* L. X *G. hirsutum* L.) hybrids of cotton. *Int. J. of Curr. Micro. and App. Sci.*, 6(10): 2883-2887.
- V.A. Kulkarni^{1*}, P.B. Wadikar², A.R. Jadhav³ and D.D. Lathe, 2024 Heterosis Studies For Yield And Yield Contributing Traits In Linseed (*Linum usitatissimum* L, VOL. XIV, ISSUE XXXXI, May, to July. 2024 Multilogic In Science ISSN 2277-7601, page 56-60.
- Vaid, R. R., Faldu, G. O. and Chaudhary, A. R. V. (2022). Heterosis study for yield and yield attributes in cotton (*Gossypium hirsutum* L.). *The Pharma Inno. J.*, 2022; 11(1): 1320-1324.
- Vavdiya, P. A., Chovatia, V. P., Madariya, R. B., Mehta, D. R. and Solanki, H. V. (2019). Heterosis studies for seed cotton yield and its components over environments in cotton. *J. of Pharma. and Phyto.*, 8(2), 2049-2053.

Table 1 Analysis of variance for for various characters in *Desi* cotton

Source of Variation	d.f.	Days to 50% flowering	Plant height	Number of sympodia/ plant	Number of bolls/plant	Boll weight	Uniformity ratio
Mean sum of squares							
Replications	1	0.56	12.66	3.36	1.96	0.01	0.01
Treatments	42	22.62**	245.34**	25.75**	14.54**	0.38**	22.11**
Error	42	0.66	14.71	4.31	1.44	0.01	0.27

Source of Variation	d.f.	Days to maturity	Ginning outturn	Upper half mean length	Fibre fineness	Fibre strength	Seed cotton yield/plant
Mean sum of squares							
Replications	1	2.61	0.15	0.00	0.01	0.02	1.30
Treatments	42	35.81**	8.34**	5.80**	0.63**	9.99**	80.59**
Error	42	0.80	2.54	0.20	0.01	0.30	0.58

*, ** significant at 5% and 1% levels, respectively

Table 3 : Top five crosses for seed cotton yield and fibre quality characters

Hybrid	Seed cotton yield per plant (gm)	Ginning out turn (%)	Upper half mean length (mm)	Fibre Fineness (micronaire) ($\mu\text{g}/\text{inch}$)	Fibre strength ($\mu\text{g}/\text{inch}$)
PA 904 x AKA 8	53.45	33.72	23.90	5.45	24.65
PA 785 x PA 810	49.85	37.27	30.35	4.30	28.95
CNA 1032 x PA 402	49.00	38.77	29.80	4.55	29.85
PA 809 x PA 08	45.75	32.99	30.25	4.95	29.90
PA 809 x JLA 505	45.60	33.97	29.50	4.40	28.80

Table 2 Estimates of heterosis in percentage over mid parent (M.P.), better parent (B.P.) and standard checks (S.C.) for various characters

Sr. No.	Hybrids	Days to 50% flowering				Days to maturity				Number of sympodia/plant			
		M.P. Heterosis (%)	B.P. Heterosis (%)	PA 740	PA 812	M.P. Heterosis (%)	B.P. Heterosis (%)	PA 740	PA 812	M.P. Heterosis (%)	B.P. Heterosis (%)	PA 740	PA 812
1	PA 785 x PA 810	-11.59 **	-12.12 **	-11.59 **	-12.12 **	-8.61 **	-9.72 **	-9.72 **	-10.44 **	25.00 *	21.62	25.00 *	12.50
2	PA 785 x PA 08	-1.81 *	-2.40 *	-0.61	-1.21	-2.86 **	-4.42 **	-3.64 **	-4.42 **	-10.77	-17.14	-19.44	-27.50 *
3	PA 785 x AKA 8	-6.88 **	-9.70 **	-9.15 **	-9.70 **	6.61 **	3.73 **	1.21	0.40	-7.46	-11.43	-13.89	-22.50 *
4	PA 785 x PA 402	-0.61	-1.21	-0.61	-1.21	-2.69 **	-2.89 **	-4.86 **	-5.62 **	13.89	10.81	13.89	2.50
5	PA 785 x JLA 505	-2.45 **	-3.64 **	-3.05 **	-3.64 **	-6.03 **	-6.22 **	-8.50 **	-9.24 **	20.00	20.00	16.67	5.00
6	PA 873 x PA 810	0.00	0.00	-0.61	-1.21	-0.41	-2.43 **	-2.43 **	-3.21 **	17.81	16.22	19.44	7.50
7	PA 873 x PA 08	-1.82 *	-2.99 **	-1.22	-1.82	-1.65 *	-4.02 **	-3.24 **	-4.02 **	-30.30 **	-36.11 **	-36.11 **	-42.50 **
8	PA 873 x AKA 8	1.26	-1.23	-1.83	-2.42 *	3.23 **	1.27	-2.83 **	-3.61 **	-44.12 **	-47.22 **	-47.22 **	-52.50 **
9	PA 873 x PA 402	2.45 **	2.45 *	1.83	1.21	-0.21	-1.24	-3.24 **	-4.02 **	9.59	8.11	11.11	0.00
10	PA 873 x JLA 505	1.85 *	1.23	0.61	0.00	2.73 **	2.08 *	-0.81	-1.61 *	32.39 **	30.56 *	30.56 *	17.50
11	PA 833 x PA 810	0.00	-1.20	0.61	0.00	1.22	0.81	0.81	0.00	9.76	0.00	25.00 *	12.50
12	PA 833 x PA 08	-2.40 **	-2.40 *	-0.61	-1.21	-2.43 **	-3.21 **	-2.43 **	-3.21 **	4.00	-13.33	8.33	-2.50
13	PA 833 x AKA 8	4.97 **	1.20	3.05 **	2.42 *	5.29 **	1.63 *	0.81	0.00	1.30	-13.33	8.33	-2.50
14	PA 833 x PA 402	-11.52 **	-12.57 **	-10.98 **	-11.52 **	-7.60 **	-8.16 **	-8.91 **	-9.64 **	-36.59 **	-42.22 **	-27.78 *	-35.00 **
15	PA 833 x JLA 505	-7.93 **	-9.58 **	-7.93 **	-8.48 **	-5.57 **	-6.53 **	-7.29 **	-8.03 **	-20.00 *	-28.89 **	-11.11	-20.00
16	PA 904 x PA 810	0.62	0.00	-0.61	-1.21	-0.42	-3.24 **	-3.24 **	-4.02 **	15.63	0.00	2.78	-7.50
17	PA 904 x PA 08	1.83 *	0.00	1.83	1.21	1.66 *	-1.61 *	-0.81	-1.61 *	8.77	3.33	-13.89	-22.50 *
18	PA 904 x AKA 8	8.23 **	6.21 **	4.27 **	3.64 **	9.33 **	8.15 **	2.02 *	1.20	32.20 *	21.88	8.33	-2.50
19	PA 904 x PA 402	-3.09 **	-3.68 **	-4.27 **	-4.85 **	-1.05	-2.89 **	-4.86 **	-5.62 **	46.88 **	27.03 *	30.56 *	17.50
20	PA 904 x JLA 505	1.24	1.24	-0.61	-1.21	1.90 **	0.42	-2.43 **	-3.21 **	38.71 **	22.86	19.44	7.50
21	PA 809 x PA 810	-4.97 **	-6.13 **	-6.71 **	-7.27 **	-3.98 **	-7.29 **	-7.29 **	-8.03 **	-21.88	-32.43 **	-30.56 *	-37.50 **
22	PA 809 x PA 08	-4.29 **	-6.59 **	-4.88 **	-5.45 **	-4.38 **	-8.03 **	-7.29 **	-8.03 **	43.86 **	36.67 *	13.89	2.50
23	PA 809 x AKA 8	-3.18 **	-4.40 **	-7.32 **	-7.88 **	-1.75 *	-2.17 *	-8.91 **	-9.64 **	52.54 **	40.63 **	25.00 *	12.50
24	PA 809 x PA 402	3.73 **	2.45 *	1.83	1.21	4.66 **	2.07 *	0.00	-0.80	9.38	-5.41	-2.78	-12.50
25	PA 809 x JLA 505	-9.38 **	-9.94 **	-11.59 **	-12.12 **	-5.11 **	-7.08 **	-9.72 **	-10.44 **	41.94 **	25.71 *	22.22	10.00
26	CNA 1032 x PA 810	0.62	0.00	-0.61	-1.21	-0.83	-3.24 **	-3.24 **	-4.02 **	-4.88	-13.33	8.33	-2.50
27	CNA 1032 x PA 08	-4.27 **	-5.99 **	-4.27 **	-4.85 **	-3.72 **	-6.43 **	-5.67 **	-6.43 **	-1.33	-17.78	2.78	-7.50
28	CNA 1032 x AKA 8	-6.33 **	-8.07 **	-9.76 **	-10.30 **	-3.67 **	-5.11 **	-9.72 **	-10.44 **	-29.87 **	-40.00 **	-25.00 *	-32.50 **
29	CNA 1032 x PA 402	-4.32 **	-4.91 **	-5.49 **	-6.06 **	-3.98 **	-5.37 **	-7.29 **	-8.03 **	9.76	0.00	25.00 *	12.50
30	CNA 1032 x JLA 505	-4.97 **	-4.97 **	-6.71 **	-7.27 **	-1.47 *	-2.50 **	-5.26 **	-6.02 **	7.50	-4.44	19.44	7.50
	S.E.+	0.68	0.78	0.78	0.78	0.79	0.91	0.91	0.91	1.81	2.09	2.09	2.09

*, ** significant at 5% and 1% levels, respectively

Table 2 Continued

Table 2 Estimates of heterosis in percentage over mid parent (M.P.), better parent (B.P.) and standard checks (S.C.) for various characters

Sr. No.	Hybrids	Number of bolls/plant				Boll weight				Plant height			
		M.P.Heterosis (%)	B.P.Heterosis (%)	PA 740	PA 812	M.P.Heterosis (%)	B.P.Heterosis (%)	PA 740	PA 812	M.P.Heterosis (%)	B.P.Heterosis (%)	PA 740	PA 812
1	PA 785 x PA 810	26.76 **	25.00 **	32.35 **	25.00 **	31.21 **	25.81 **	25.33 **	22.76 **	11.30 **	3.91	1.92	5.56
2	PA 785 x PA 08	-5.71	-5.71	-2.94	-8.33	-4.88	-7.14	-10.86 *	-12.69 **	7.66 **	2.02	-3.07	0.40
3	PA 785 x AKA 8	-18.31 **	-19.44 **	-14.71 *	-19.44 **	-16.09 **	-17.93 **	-21.52 **	-23.13 **	0.88	-0.87	-12.64 **	-9.52 **
4	PA 785 x PA 402	33.33 **	25.71 **	29.41 **	22.22 **	29.91 **	28.19 **	20.38 **	17.91 **	19.64 **	19.37 **	1.53	5.16
5	PA 785 x JLA 505	22.39 **	17.14 *	20.59 **	13.89 *	29.79 **	27.08 **	16.19 **	13.81 **	16.25 **	8.14 **	6.90 *	10.71 **
6	PA 873 x PA 810	-13.89 *	-13.89 *	-8.82	-13.89 *	-21.72 **	-25.13 **	-18.29 **	-19.96 **	6.15 *	4.55	5.75	9.52 **
7	PA 873 x PA 08	-23.94 **	-25.00 **	-20.59 **	-25.00 **	7.52 *	1.05	10.29 *	8.02	-0.78	-3.79	-2.68	0.79
8	PA 873 x AKA 8	5.56	5.56	11.76	5.56	13.12 **	6.11	15.81 **	13.43 **	0.00	-6.44 *	-5.36	-1.98
9	PA 873 x PA 402	-1.49	-8.33	-2.94	-8.33	-23.64 **	-28.97 **	-22.48 **	-24.07 **	-8.04 **	-15.53 **	-14.56 **	-11.51 **
10	PA 873 x JLA 505	-8.82	-13.89 *	-8.82	-13.89 *	7.45 *	-3.14	5.71	3.54	7.28 **	6.06 *	7.28 *	11.11 **
11	PA 833 x PA 810	-29.27 **	-36.96 **	-14.71 *	-19.44 **	2.71	-2.10	-2.48	-4.48	-4.92	-9.38 **	-11.11 **	-7.94 *
12	PA 833 x PA 08	-8.64	-19.57 **	8.82	2.78	16.56 **	13.10 **	8.57 *	6.34	7.50 **	4.03	-1.15	2.38
13	PA 833 x AKA 8	-24.39 **	-32.61 **	-8.82	-13.89 *	6.35	3.39	-1.14	-3.17	0.43	0.00	-11.11 **	-7.94 *
14	PA 833 x PA 402	-29.87 **	-41.30 **	-20.59 **	-25.00 **	-23.06 **	-24.54 **	-29.14 **	-30.60 **	18.32 **	15.52 **	2.68	6.35 *
15	PA 833 x JLA 505	-25.64 **	-36.96 **	-14.71 *	-19.44 **	-25.05 **	-26.16 **	-33.33 **	-34.70 **	-14.69 **	-18.99 **	-19.92 **	-17.06 **
16	PA 904 x PA 810	7.69	-2.78	2.94	-2.78	8.12 *	8.02	7.81	5.60	5.65 *	5.45	3.83	7.54 *
17	PA 904 x PA 08	3.13	-5.71	-2.94	-8.33	9.34 *	7.25	7.05	4.85	-2.97	-4.67	-6.13 *	-2.78
18	PA 904 x AKA 8	-4.62	-13.89 *	-8.82	-13.89 *	-27.88 **	-29.39 **	-29.52 **	-30.97 **	-19.51 **	-23.74 **	-24.90 **	-22.22 **
19	PA 904 x PA 402	43.33 **	38.71 **	26.47 **	19.44 **	34.51 **	30.53 **	30.29 **	27.61 **	9.21 **	1.56	0.00	3.57

20	PA 904 x JLA 505	27.87 **	21.88 **	14.71 *	8.33	25.20 **	17.56 **	17.33 **	14.93 **	-1.36	-1.55	-2.68	0.79
21	PA 809 x PA 810	-7.94	-19.44 **	-14.71 *	-19.44 **	-15.80 **	-16.44 **	-16.76 **	-18.47 **	-11.42 **	-12.11 **	-13.79 **	-10.71 **
22	PA 809 x PA 08	32.26 **	17.14 *	20.59 **	13.89 *	18.35 **	17.09 **	14.86 **	12.50 **	6.40 *	5.56	1.92	5.56
23	PA 809 x AKA 8	23.81 **	8.33	14.71 *	8.33	24.48 **	22.91 **	20.57 **	18.10 **	14.11 **	9.13 **	5.36	9.13 **
24	PA 809 x PA 402	20.69 **	12.90	2.94	-2.78	7.14	4.85	2.86	0.75	9.09 **	2.38	-1.15	2.38
25	PA 809 x JLA 505	38.98 **	28.13 **	20.59 **	13.89 *	34.97 **	27.77 **	25.33 **	22.76 **	7.84 **	6.59 *	5.36	9.13 **
26	CNA 1032 x PA 810	-3.70	-13.33 *	14.71 *	8.33	16.30 **	15.97 **	16.19 **	13.81 **	12.79 **	5.08	3.07	6.75 *
27	CNA 1032 x PA 08	-17.50 **	-26.67 **	-2.94	-8.33	-3.30	-5.32	-5.14	-7.09	-2.35	-7.66 *	-12.26 **	-9.13 **
28	CNA 1032 x AKA 8	-33.33 **	-40.00 **	-20.59 **	-25.00 **	-30.74 **	-32.32 **	-32.19 **	-33.58 **	-12.64 **	-14.35 **	-24.52 **	-21.83 **
29	CNA 1032 x PA 402	5.26	-11.11 *	17.65 *	11.11	28.95 **	24.90 **	25.14 **	22.57 **	25.34 **	25.34 **	6.13 *	9.92 **
30	CNA 1032 x JLA 505	1.30	-13.33 *	14.71 *	8.33	29.01 **	20.91 **	21.14 **	18.66 **	8.14 **	0.39	-0.77	2.78
	S.E. _±	1.01	1.17	1.17	1.17	0.09	0.10	0.10	0.10	3.25	3.75	3.75	3.75

*, ** significant at 5% and 1% levels, respectively

Table 2 Continued

Table 2 Estimates of heterosis in percentage over mid parent (M.P.), better parent (B.P.) and standard checks (S.C.) for various characters

Sr. No.	Hybrids	Ginning outturn				Upper half mean length				Fibre fineness / Micronaire			
		M.P. Heterosis (%)	B.P. Heterosis (%)	PA 740	PA 812	M.P. Heterosis (%)	B.P. Heterosis (%)	PA 740	PA 812	M.P. Heterosis (%)	B.P. Heterosis (%)	PA 740	PA 812
1	PA 785 x PA 810	4.19	2.38	3.04	8.99	5.47 **	4.48 **	7.62 **	1.68	-23.89 **	-23.89 **	-10.42 **	-8.51 **
2	PA 785 x PA 08	4.39	4.31	1.34	7.20	-0.62	-1.40	-0.35	-5.86 **	-25.89 **	-26.55 **	-13.54 **	-11.70 **
3	PA 785 x AKA 8	-13.49 **	-14.50 **	-16.94 **	-12.14 *	-8.57 **	-10.18 **	-9.22 **	-14.24 **	-29.96 **	-33.06 **	-13.54 **	-11.70 **
4	PA 785 x PA 402	-3.67	-4.80	-7.51	-2.16	5.34 **	2.11	3.19	-2.51	-14.67 **	-15.04 **	0.00	2.13
5	PA 785 x JLA 505	8.15	6.45	3.41	9.39	4.31 **	4.04 *	5.14 **	-0.67	-23.68 **	-24.35 **	-9.38 **	-7.45 **
6	PA 873 x PA 810	-7.81	-8.49	-6.53	-1.13	-6.66 **	-7.06 **	-4.26 *	-9.55 **	1.35	0.00	17.71 **	20.21 **
7	PA 873 x PA 08	-11.00 **	-13.24 **	-11.38 *	-6.26	-4.49 **	-5.73 **	-3.72 *	-9.05 **	-15.84 **	-16.22 **	-3.13	-1.06
8	PA 873 x AKA 8	-1.87	-5.36	-3.33	2.25	5.33 **	2.95	5.14 **	-0.67	-12.82 **	-17.74 **	6.25 *	8.51 **
9	PA 873 x PA 402	-13.09 **	-16.17 **	-14.38 **	-9.43	-6.03 **	-9.37 **	-7.45 **	-12.56 **	0.90	0.00	16.67 **	19.15 **
10	PA 873 x JLA 505	-3.46	-7.27	-5.28	0.19	-0.44	-1.22	0.89	-4.69 **	-0.44	-2.61	16.67 **	19.15 **

11	PA 833 x PA 810	-6.53	-10.98 *	-10.40 *	-5.22	-4.90 **	-8.09 **	-5.32 **	-10.55 **	-5.49 **	-9.68 **	16.67 **	19.15 **
12	PA 833 x PA 08	4.93	1.72	-1.33	4.37	7.52 **	5.70 **	5.14 **	-0.67	-2.13	-7.26 **	19.79 **	22.34 **
13	PA 833 x AKA 8	5.15	3.05	-2.23	3.42	5.13 **	4.36 *	1.77	-3.85 *	-15.32 **	-15.32 **	9.38 **	11.70 **
14	PA 833 x PA 402	-2.21	-4.17	-9.07	-3.82	-11.23 **	-11.81 **	-15.25 **	-19.93 **	-17.80 **	-21.77 **	1.04	3.19
15	PA 833 x JLA 505	2.16	0.53	-5.42	0.04	-6.22 **	-8.29 **	-7.80 **	-12.90 **	-13.81 **	-16.94 **	7.29 **	9.57 **
16	PA 904 x PA 810	-9.46 *	-9.89 *	-8.43	-3.14	-1.13	-1.72	1.24	-4.36 **	-19.44 **	-23.01 **	-9.38 **	-7.45 **
17	PA 904 x PA 08	-4.37	-6.54	-5.03	0.45	3.44 *	2.26	4.08 *	-1.68	-0.93	-4.50 *	10.42 **	12.77 **
18	PA 904 x AKA 8	-5.12	-8.26	-6.77	-1.39	-14.95 **	-16.72 **	-15.25 **	-19.93 **	-3.96 *	-12.10 **	13.54 **	15.96 **
19	PA 904 x PA 402	9.79 *	6.15	7.87	14.10 **	9.47 **	5.75 **	7.62 **	1.68	-17.21 **	-20.54 **	-7.29 **	-5.32 *
20	PA 904 x JLA 505	-2.66	-6.27	-4.76	0.75	3.77 *	3.14	4.96 **	-0.84	1.83	-3.48	15.63 **	18.09 **
21	PA 809 x PA 810	-8.94 *	-9.30 *	-8.71	-3.44	-14.01 **	-14.97 **	-12.41 **	-17.25 **	-4.04 *	-5.31 *	11.46 **	13.83 **
22	PA 809 x PA 08	-7.32	-8.64	-8.78	-3.51	7.17 **	6.51 **	7.27 **	1.34	-10.41 **	-10.81 **	3.13	5.32 *
23	PA 809 x AKA 8	9.27 *	6.55	6.39	12.53 *	6.08 **	4.40 **	5.14 **	-0.67	-24.79 **	-29.03 **	-8.33 **	-6.38 *
24	PA 809 x PA 402	-3.86	-6.24	-6.39	-0.98	8.43 **	5.28 **	6.03 **	0.17	-1.80	-2.68	13.54 **	15.96 **
25	PA 809 x JLA 505	-3.14	-5.94	-6.08	-0.66	3.96 **	3.87 *	4.61 **	-1.17	-21.78 **	-23.48 **	-8.33 **	-6.38 *
26	CNA 1032 x PA 810	-2.16	-3.16	-2.53	3.10	3.19 *	3.10	6.21 **	0.34	-5.73 **	-6.14 **	11.46 **	13.83 **
27	CNA 1032 x PA 08	-10.38 *	-11.10 *	-12.35 *	-7.28	-7.62 **	-9.14 **	-6.56 **	-11.73 **	0.44	-0.88	17.71 **	20.21 **
28	CNA 1032 x AKA 8	-10.37 *	-12.06 *	-13.29 **	-8.28	-4.96 **	-7.41 **	-4.79 **	-10.05 **	-3.36 *	-7.26 **	19.79 **	22.34 **
29	CNA 1032 x PA 402	10.81 *	8.72	7.20	13.40 **	6.91 **	2.76	5.67 **	-0.17	-19.47 **	-20.18 **	-5.21 *	-3.19
30	CNA 1032 x JLA 505	0.87	-1.44	-2.82	2.79	2.35	1.21	4.08 *	-1.68	-18.78 **	-19.13 **	-3.13	-1.06
	S.E. _±	1.41	1.62	1.62	1.62	0.39	0.45	0.45	0.45	0.09	0.11	0.11	0.11

*, ** significant at 5% and 1% levels, respectively

Table 2 Continued

Table 2 Estimates of heterosis in percentage over mid parent (M.P.), better parent (B.P.) and standard checks (S.C.) for various characters

Sr. No.	Hybrids	Fibre strength				Uniformity Ratio				Seed cotton yield/plant			
		M.P. Heterosis (%)	B.P. Heterosis (%)	PA 740	PA 812	M.P. Heterosis (%)	B.P. Heterosis (%)	PA 740	PA 812	M.P. Heterosis (%)	B.P. Heterosis (%)	PA 740	PA 812
1	PA 785 x PA 810	6.73 **	4.70 *	5.85 **	6.43 **	5.00 **	4.35 **	5.66 **	4.35 **	44.91 **	41.82 **	42.02 **	32.58 **
2	PA 785 x PA 08	1.69	1.31	-0.73	-0.18	-5.63 **	-6.21 **	-5.03 **	-6.21 **	8.01 **	5.06 *	6.55 **	-0.53
3	PA 785 x AKA 8	0.48	-1.32	-4.02	-3.49	-10.56 **	-11.66 **	-9.43 **	-10.56 **	8.18 **	7.31 **	4.56 *	-2.39
4	PA 785 x PA 402	14.31 **	12.59 **	9.51 **	10.11 **	2.52 **	2.52 **	2.52 **	1.24	25.57 **	25.30 **	20.66 **	12.63 **
5	PA 785 x JLA 505	11.56 **	9.84 **	10.24 **	10.85 **	7.69 **	5.66 **	5.66 **	4.35 **	32.23 **	30.16 **	24.79 **	16.49 **
6	PA 873 x PA 810	-2.72	-2.89	-1.83	-1.29	-4.97 **	-4.97 **	-3.77 **	-4.97 **	-3.92 *	-5.50 *	-2.14	-8.64 **

7	PA 873 x PA 08	-3.77 *	-5.08 *	-4.39 *	-3.86	-2.48 **	-2.48 **	-1.26	-2.48 **	6.46 **	5.36 *	9.12 **	1.86
8	PA 873 x AKA 8	9.96 **	6.17 **	6.95 **	7.54 **	2.47 **	1.84 **	4.40 **	3.11 **	21.47 **	17.88 **	22.08 **	13.96 **
9	PA 873 x PA 402	-6.09 **	-9.07 **	-8.41 **	-7.90 **	-1.88 **	-2.48 **	-1.26	-2.48 **	3.35	-0.28	3.28	-3.59
10	PA 873 x JLA 505	3.09	2.90	3.66	4.23 *	7.01 **	4.35 **	5.66 **	4.35 **	18.93 **	12.79 **	16.81 **	9.04 **
11	PA 833 x PA 810	-14.90 **	-17.36 **	-16.45 **	-15.99 **	1.27 *	-1.24	0.00	-1.24	10.81 **	4.98 *	5.13 *	-1.86
12	PA 833 x PA 08	11.07 **	9.51 **	7.31 **	7.90 **	5.73 **	3.11 **	4.40 **	3.11 **	21.25 **	14.19 **	15.81 **	8.11 **
13	PA 833 x AKA 8	1.55	0.77	-4.02	-3.49	-1.27 *	-4.29 **	-1.89 **	-3.11 **	11.04 **	6.58 **	3.85	-3.06
14	PA 833 x PA 402	-15.33 **	-15.74 **	-19.74 **	-19.30 **	-6.41 **	-8.18 **	-8.18 **	-9.32 **	-12.49 **	-15.53 **	-18.66 **	-24.07 **
15	PA 833 x JLA 505	-9.35 **	-11.66 **	-11.33 **	-10.85 **	2.61 **	2.61 **	-1.26	-2.48 **	-20.06 **	-21.47 **	-27.07 **	-31.91 **
16	PA 904 x PA 810	5.69 **	5.60 **	6.95 **	7.54 **	5.73 **	3.11 **	4.40 **	3.11 **	18.67 **	13.94 **	14.10 **	6.52 **
17	PA 904 x PA 08	4.77 *	3.07	4.39 *	4.96 *	7.64 **	4.97 **	6.29 **	4.97 **	15.38 **	10.11 **	11.68 **	4.26 *
18	PA 904 x AKA 8	-7.59 **	-11.01 **	-9.87 **	-9.38 **	-3.80 **	-6.75 **	-4.40 **	-5.59 **	-20.51 **	-22.66 **	-24.64 **	-29.65 **
19	PA 904 x PA 402	11.59 **	7.76 **	9.14 **	9.74 **	8.97 **	6.92 **	6.92 **	5.59 **	61.60 **	58.14 **	52.28 **	42.15 **
20	PA 904 x JLA 505	5.89 **	5.42 *	6.76 **	7.35 **	8.50 **	8.50 **	4.40 **	3.11 **	35.64 **	35.12 **	25.50 **	17.15 **
21	PA 809 x PA 810	-21.45 **	-23.51 **	-22.67 **	-22.24 **	-2.21 **	-3.73 **	-2.52 **	-3.73 **	-12.91 **	-13.15 **	-12.54 **	-18.35 **
22	PA 809 x PA 08	12.83 **	11.57 **	9.32 **	9.93 **	2.84 **	1.24	2.52 **	1.24	28.96 **	28.51 **	30.34 **	21.68 **
23	PA 809 x AKA 8	13.98 **	12.79 **	8.04 **	8.64 **	4.70 **	2.45 **	5.03 **	3.73 **	25.09 **	23.06 **	23.93 **	15.69 **
24	PA 809 x PA 402	10.77 **	9.92 **	5.30 *	5.88 **	4.13 **	3.14 **	3.14 **	1.86 **	20.46 **	17.82 **	18.66 **	10.77 **
25	PA 809 x JLA 505	7.36 **	4.92 *	5.30 *	5.88 **	8.74 **	7.69 **	5.66 **	4.35 **	34.22 **	29.00 **	29.91 **	21.28 **
26	CNA 1032 x PA 810	1.71	1.07	3.47	4.04	1.86 **	1.86 **	3.14 **	1.86 **	22.81 **	21.19 **	24.64 **	16.36 **
27	CNA 1032 x PA 08	-7.48 **	-9.46 **	-7.31 **	-6.80 **	-4.35 **	-4.35 **	-3.14 **	-4.35 **	0.14	-0.55	2.28	-4.52 *
28	CNA 1032 x AKA 8	-13.70 **	-17.32 **	-15.36 **	-14.89 **	-9.88 **	-10.43 **	-8.18 **	-9.32 **	-29.73 **	-31.58 **	-29.63 **	-34.31 **
29	CNA 1032 x PA 402	10.97 **	6.61 **	9.14 **	9.74 **	3.75 **	3.11 **	4.40 **	3.11 **	40.20 **	35.73 **	39.60 **	30.32 **
30	CNA 1032 x JLA 505	4.24 *	3.21	5.67 **	6.25 **	4.46 **	1.86 **	3.14 **	1.86 **	29.11 **	22.85 **	26.35 **	17.95 **
	S.E. _±	0.48	0.55	0.55	0.55	0.44	0.51	0.51	0.51	0.66	0.77	0.77	0.77